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Press Release

The Learning Makes Sense initiative presents recommendations for a complex improvement of the education system in Slovakia

MESA10, a not-for-profit organisation, launched the **Learning Makes Sense** initiative in 2016 with the aim of identifying the causes of the current unfavourable state of the education system in Slovakia, and recommending appropriate systemic changes. In October 2019 the initiative published [its Analysis of Findings about the State of the Education System in Slovakia](#), describing the major problems in the education system, together with the causes, relationships and impacts which prevent us from achieving the envisaged state in education and research. The analysis was based on an extensive qualitative and quantitative survey, with more than 650 interviewees and 15,000 survey respondents from among various educators and employers.

As an answer to the problems and causes indicated, the *Learning Makes Sense* initiative presents its **Recommendations for a Complex Improvement of the Education System in Slovakia**, from pre-primary up to higher education institutions, including research and artistic activities at Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The recommendations will be presented at conferences held in Bratislava (27 February), Banská Bystrica (26 March) and Košice (27 March). The recommendations are also based on the **best practices** in Slovak education, which were identified both by the team members during their qualitative survey, and gathered from almost **a hundred stakeholders implementing them** and reporting their activities on the [Learning Makes Sense web page](#). Best practices illustrate that despite the unfavourable state of the education system as such, many schools, not-for-profit organisations and other institutions currently offer innovations and positive changes to their students, teachers and other staff. Another inspiration for the recommendations presented were **best practices from abroad**. Project team members gathered these practices during their study visits in several countries, where numerous consultations with experts at various international organisations took place (e.g. OECD, EUA, EURASHE, ENQA), as well as by studying **education policy analyses** concerning various issues in the international context.

The **Recommendations for a Complex Improvement of the Education System in Slovakia** are based on three principles. The first principle is increasing

the **quality of education** at all educational levels, i.e. from pre-primary to higher education, including **research**, at higher education institutions. The second principle is ensuring **equality of opportunities** for all children and students facing various barriers in their access to education resulting from health or social disadvantages. The third principle is emphasising the **well-being of children, students and teachers**, along with other staff **at schools**, so that they all learn and work in a pleasant environment and a positive atmosphere.

The recommendations presented by the *Learning Makes Sense* initiative seek to bring about a **complex reform of the education system, including research, at HEIs in Slovakia**. Renáta Hall, the project director, emphasises that: *“Since individual recommendations are closely inter-related, they cannot be implemented as minor amendments to the system in place. When formulating the recommendations, we stressed that all stakeholders in the education system must first be provided with sufficient support. Only after that can we expect them to implement the changes in practice.”* The *Learning Makes Sense* initiative perceives that improving the education system in Slovakia is a **systemic and ongoing process**. After drafting and implementing any reform, it is always important to thoroughly evaluate its impacts and make further adjustments and improvements.

At the core of the recommendations proposed is a **new model of the education system**, which is **open, permeable and flexible**. In this model, all learners are prepared to proceed to higher educational levels and employment without any risk of being trapped in “dead end” education tracks and finishing their studies with no work qualification. Katarína Vančíková, an analyst in the *Learning Makes Sense* project, explained: *“We have to focus on the early years of each child. Therefore, developing quality early childhood care and education programmes and providing universal access to them for all should become a real priority. It is important to guarantee each child a place in such programmes, and create a strong network of early intervention providers to support families and children with health and social disadvantages, right from birth.”* We also recommend extending the first stage at primary schools by 1 year. The second stage at primary schools should be extended by a voluntary Year 10, which could help some pupils complete primary school and continue in further education according to their abilities and interests. In secondary education, we propose introducing a first year with a common general educational programme at all secondary education programmes, with a school-leaving exam allowing for subsequent specialisation in further years of secondary education. According to Renáta Hall, in tertiary education it is important *“...to support applied studies both by enhancing professional Bachelor programs and introducing applied learning in the academically-oriented study programmes”*. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) should open up. Both students and academic staff should participate more in mobilities abroad, and international students and academic staff should become an integral part of our HEIs. We recommend that the government supports the participation of our academics in international

projects e.g. by financing projects with a positive assessment in the Horizon Europe scheme.

Regarding **the content of education, teaching methods and assessment in education**, we recommend elaborating a new national curriculum for particular educational levels. Along with updated content and education goals, the new national curriculum should outline recommended strategies for teaching and assessment, and thus provide teachers with a practical guide to implementing changes in their classes. The analyst Petra Fridrichová explains: *"In the first stage of primary education, we recommend that learning is structured in larger blocks, enabling teachers to apply various active teaching methods. In the second stage of primary education, we aim to support learning in context by structuring the content of education into learning areas. Secondary schools should focus on developing professional knowledge and skills in particular subjects, with grammar schools emphasizing knowledge and secondary vocational schools focusing on the combination of skills and knowledge. Hence, we propose that the content of education should have a modular structure, and the recommended combination of school subjects should be determined in consultation with employers"*. In the first stage of primary education, we also recommend that assessment by numerical marks should be replaced by narrative description, thus strengthening motivation for further learning and describing the strengths of each pupil and areas for further improvement.

To improve the quality of teaching and ethical behaviour at **Higher Education Institutions** we recommend **establishing centres for developing the teaching skills** of academic staff and decreasing the number of teaching contact hours. *"Vigorous compliance to ethical standards in academia from students, teachers and research or artistic staff at HEIs is crucial in our opinion, and both students and HEI teachers should be trained in this field. Also, HEIs should use software tools to detect plagiarism, develop and implement their Codes of Conduct, and withdraw any fraudulently received university degrees"*, explained the analyst Stanislav Lukáč.

Recommendations concerning **customised support for learners** are based on acknowledging that all learners have varying needs, potential and interests, and that support should be provided to all learners requiring it. *"However, the support should not stem from simple diagnosis, but rather from the specific learning needs of individual children and students. The education system should provide support measures at six distinct levels, with all schools entitled to receive such support. Furthermore, the government should fund these support measures adequately and in a flexible way"*, emphasised the analyst Miroslava Hapalová. Since the introduction of **claimable support measures** in education will require increased personnel capacities, we recommend that **each school is granted the opportunity to employ a SEN teacher or other professional staff**, and that **support teams** operate at primary and secondary schools. We also recommend

establishing **advisory and prevention centres at HEIs**. Furthermore, special focus should be placed on the transition of students from special needs to mainstream schools. Here, so-called **transition plans**, along with financial contributions to special schools, should support mainstream schools in managing the transition of students successfully.

To **improve the performance of teachers, researchers and academic staff** we propose making **their remuneration more attractive**, so that the ratio of teachers' wages to the wages of the university educated workforce in Slovakia matches the OECD average. We propose that the same principle is applied to **HEI staff**, currently lagging 10 percentage points behind the wages of the general workforce with a PhD degree. *"In pre-service teacher training, we recommend extending teaching internships for students and increasing their quality, along with specialised training in general and subject-based didactics, so that graduates gain not only theoretical knowledge on what to teach, but most especially the practical teaching skills on how to teach"*, explained Jozef Miškolci, an analyst in the Learning Makes Sense project. **Also, teachers must be trained to be able to customise their teaching and address the variety of learners' needs and interests.** Therefore, we propose that special needs education and inclusive education become mandatory subjects in pre-service teacher training. We also suggest that teachers and professional staff at schools should have access to quality and diverse in-service teacher training programmes. The informal networking of schools should also be supported. **To improve the quality of doctoral studies** we recommend **establishing doctoral schools** where both research and applied or soft skills are developed. We recommend **abolishing academic title "Professor" and "Docent" and establishing specific job positions** with high quality research, artistic and/or teaching performance as the main qualification criteria. *"This will contribute to the opening up of our HEIs to academic staff from abroad, and also to younger academic staff,"* explained Renáta Hall.

For **effective management** of the education system and individual schools, providing adequate funding and high-quality staff in management positions is a must. The analyst Peter Drál emphasizes: *"At schools we need quality school management and teacher leadership. Therefore, we recommend adjusting the qualification criteria set for management staff and allowing for a more flexible management structure. School principals and rectors should be relieved of their operational duties and receive quality training in becoming effective team leaders improving the learning environment and setting and implementing long-term development goals for their schools."* We propose that a **Manager of the Year in Education and Research award** is established to recognise the work carried out by managers in schools and share best practices. At HEIs we propose **simplifying management processes** and **strengthening the rector's position. Rectors should be selected rigorously** by the supervisory board and academic senate. *"The academic senate should nominate almost half of the supervisory board*

members and thus the connection of the board to the HEI shall be strengthened”, adds Renáta Hall. Compared to the EU average, Slovakia lags significantly behind in research funding and **resources for research should be increased**. Also, introducing performance contracts between HEIs and the Ministry of Education, Research and Sport should provide more **predictability, stability and diversity in the profiling of HEIs**.

During 2021–2027, Slovakia will again receive **hundreds of millions in EUROS from EU structural and investment funds**. These resources could provide **the basis for launching many of the proposed reforms**. Therefore, it is **necessary to improve their implementation** by contracting at least half of the resources up until 2024, reducing the administrative burden of beneficiaries and simplifying the procedures.

Full-text recommendations presented by the *Learning Makes Sense* initiative for further discussion by professionals and the wider public are available at: <https://todarozum.sk/>

THE PROJECT IS SUPPORTED BY

Press Release – Annex

Area 1: Permeable, open and flexible education system

All children should start schooling on an equal footing, so that they can proceed with their peers on to further educational levels without any risk of being trapped in “dead end” education tracks and not developing to their full potential. Therefore, we recommend **establishing an integrated system of early childhood education and care with universal access** (ECEC). This system should guarantee various support services for all children and their families, from birth until children commence their schooling. At the same time, we propose the gradual introduction of a **legal entitlement to a place in ECEC** for all children aged 3 and above. We also propose that the whole ECEC system is included in the Ministry of Education domain and is governed by a new law. We propose that **kindergartens open up to enrol all children from the age of 6 months up until they commence schooling and that crèches gradually make the transition to becoming kindergartens**. An important proposal is **the creation of an accessible network of early intervention providers** for all children with physical disabilities or social disadvantages, as well as for their families. This support should be provided mainly in the family environment.

In the integrated ECEC system, emphasis should be placed on customised support and early intervention. It is therefore crucial to **provide quality ongoing diagnosis, stimulate child development in a targeted manner and carry out screening assessments for school readiness** of all children aged 5. We recommend that enrolment to school be based solely on a child's age. This relates to our proposal to **abolish the option to postpone the start of compulsory schooling in the medium term**. It is also vital that schools better address the adaptation of newly enrolled children, so that performance pressures are reduced and the practice of repeating years is eliminated.

We propose that a new national curriculum for primary education is developed, and that the **first stage of primary school should last 5 years (ISCED1)**, split into 2 modules. The first 3-year module should allow sufficient time for pupils to adapt to school, and to develop their language and communication skills, reading literacy and learning strategies, while respecting their individual pace of learning. The next two years should provide for a gradual transition to a further stage of education.

The learning environment at primary schools should be such that there is no reason to create any parallel educational tracks. Therefore we also propose **a change of national curriculum for lower secondary education (ISCED2)**. Here, a choice of various educational content should be supported, so that each pupil can discover and develop their strengths. With support from the career guidance advisor, each

pupil at primary school should choose their secondary school so that it matches their abilities and interests.

All pupils should have the opportunity to continue in further studies at secondary school. Therefore, we propose that those pupils who would not succeed in the final assessment at the end of the ISCED2 educational stage study further in a programme without a school-leaving exam at any secondary school. To improve one's chances of completing the secondary school-leaving exam, an option to **retake at any later time shall be made available, along with the option to extend schooling at primary school by one year** in the optional Year 10.

No student should leave secondary school without acquiring a work qualification. This can be addressed by an **upgraded model of secondary vocational education**, according to which each school leaver receives a certificate stating a specific qualification level according to the National Qualifications Framework. The curriculum of study programmes with a school-leaving exam at secondary vocational schools and grammar schools assumes that students are preparing for tertiary education, and are **gradually profiling themselves by selecting subject-based modules at a medium or advanced level**. Greater permeability in secondary education should be promoted by **a one-year common general educational programme on all tracks, with a school-leaving exam**. During this year, students can revise their choice of school and move to another school if they so wish.

The general trend of massification in tertiary education means that it is necessary to offer a more diverse range of study programmes, addressing the needs of a more diverse student body. We recommend **expanding the range of study programmes with professional Bachelor program**, so that their graduates can enter the labour market immediately following completion of such programmes. It is also necessary to **link academically-oriented study programmes to practice**. A more diverse student population automatically exacerbates the need to **improve study success at HEIs** for all students, including those with special educational needs.

Slovak Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) should also **become more international**, i.e. get more students and academics participating in international mobilities, and attract and integrate international students and academics. **International students and post-docs** should be **supported financially by awarding scholarships**. It is also necessary to increase the participation of our academic staff in international research, art and teaching projects. The **administrative units dealing with international issues at HEIs should become more professionalised**. It is also necessary to stimulate development of the **project centres** helping HEIs to gain and administer international projects. It would also be advantageous if **projects with a positive assessment by**

European experts in the Horizon Europe scheme were supported by the government, e.g. through European structural and investment funds.

Area 2: The content of education, teaching methods and assessment in education

The content of education should support holistic personality development, critical thinking, digital skills, motivation to study and work, ability to learn in context and co-operation in problem solving. The content of education should be attractive and up-to-date. Yet neither the current content of education nor the teaching and assessment methods applied conform to these requirements. The current national curricula for individual educational levels also contributes to this state of affairs, as it is available in multiple versions for children with various needs. Therefore, we propose **unifying the national curriculum** for individual educational levels so that all learners can develop their own potential systemically, and their diverse needs are respected. To achieve these goals, a new national curriculum is vital, with updated content and objectives, along with a description of recommended teaching strategies and assessment methods. Such a measure aims to **provide teachers with support in changing their mode of instruction** in learning areas at primary schools and school subjects at secondary schools.

The teaching methods used should **support active learning and make education more customised**, and assessment methods also need to be changed. In primary education, we recommend placing emphasis on reading literacy, and adapting teaching strategies so that broader thematic areas and longer time blocks can be applied. At this education level, we also recommend **replacing assessment by numeric marks with narrative description**. This should enhance not only knowledge acquisition, but especially learners' motivation to study and their adoption of effective learning strategies. In the second stage of primary school, we aim to support the development of skills, knowledge and competences in **certain learning areas, using a broad range of teaching methods** and emphasising ongoing formative assessment. We propose the effective use of IT in the learning process. At secondary schools, **knowledge and skills in individual school subjects should be further developed**. Study programmes (with or without school-leaving exams) should be structured in such a way that students can sufficiently profile themselves by their choice of school subject, and at the same time develop their general and professional competences in a balanced way.

We propose that innovations and best practices in education should be shared on the existing Central Storage of Digital Educational Content online portal. **Teaching resources created and peer-reviewed by teachers** should also be published there. We also recommend linking the development of textbooks and learning resources to research. Each textbook should be tested in practice, and should

include versions suitable for students with disadvantages or disabilities. We propose that **textbooks should be approved after a review process**, including an assessment by both an expert in the respective field, and an expert in didactics for the particular subject.

At HEIs, we recommend creating tools **to improve instruction and ethical behaviour in academic work and research**. We recommend applying **active teaching methods, regularly updating the content of education, and linking theoretical knowledge to practice**. Study at HEIs could be made more attractive by **making the curriculum more international** and by the broader use of English in instruction. This could also increase the number of foreign students at Slovak HEIs. Stronger support is also required for **the participation of HEI students on mobilities abroad**, and HEIs could contribute by scheduling so-called mobility windows in their study programmes.

Improving instruction at HEIs should be the core task of the **centres for developing teaching skills** of both PhD students and academic staff at HEIs. The centres should also help the academic staff at HEIs in transforming their study programmes. We also propose **revising the structure of study programmes** and **decreasing the number of subjects taught and contact teaching hours**. We recommend establishing **programme boards** to coordinate the **views of teachers, students and employers** on study programmes. During the transformation of study programmes, teachers should be relieved of other tasks, and they should be remunerated for performing the transformation tasks. We also propose an **award for the best HEI teachers** at each HEI, as well as overall in Slovakia. Education at HEIs should be more interlinked with practice **by extending the scope and quality of student internships**. This can be achieved by making student internships an integral part of studies, monitoring their progress, and making a subsequent evaluation of their impacts. We also propose that HEIs more frequently engage various professionals from the corporate sector in classes.

An important recommendation is to increase **compliance with the Code of Conduct at HEIs by students, teachers and research/artistic staff**. To achieve this, HEIs should adopt various preventative, detection and sanction mechanisms against cheating, unethical behaviour and misconduct. Plagiarism can be avoided by the **thorough training of students in academic writing**, from the commencement of their studies at HEIs. The **Central Registrar of Academic Theses** is used to **detect plagiarised papers**. It would be useful to enlarge it with a register of **academic essays** submitted by students, in order to better facilitate plagiarism detection for teachers. Compliance with the Code of Academic and Research Conduct by students and academics should be supervised by **Ethics Committees at HEIs and the National Ethics Committee for Academic and Research Integrity**. A **legal act enabling the withdrawal of any fraudulently obtained academic degrees** should be prepared and adopted forthwith. In the

case that a **Slovak Accreditation Agency** finds out that a HEI **is not implementing processes to detect academic misconduct in the long term, and continues to do so despite warnings**, we propose **that the agency initiates proceedings** and imposes punitive measures on such an HEI.

Area 3: Customised support for learners

The education system should **recognise the diverse educational needs, potential and interests** of all learners, address them, and provide learners with quality and customised support in case of need. Therefore, we recommend replacing the current model of grouping students based on their disabilities, social disadvantages or talents **with a vertical model based on the assessment of the required need for support in education** that is vital to the full **development of each learner's potential**. Support in education should be available to **all learners to the extent they need it**, and it should not only reflect shortcomings on the side of a learner (e.g. physical disability), but also the barriers in access to education at a particular school (e.g. existence of physical barriers, language of instruction differing from the learner's mother tongue).

Diagnosing educational needs should help in the **early detection of at risk development and establishing effective support**. Therefore, we propose defining **standards in diagnosis**. The main role of diagnosis should be to identify the learner's potential and existent barriers in learning, as well as to design appropriate support measures and services. At the same time, we propose **a significant increase in the personnel and material capacities of advisory and prevention centres**. Diagnosing should also be carried out by professional staff at schools, and their findings should help in the design of effective learning strategies and support measures.

Support measures in education should be **available to all learners** that need them, and funding should **be guaranteed for schools**. We propose preparing **a catalogue of support measures** grouped into **general, targeted and specific measures**. The support measures should include e.g. extra hours for certain subjects, adjusted content of education, SEN support and interventions, additional support from teaching assistants, care and assistance from support staff, and other support measures currently not provided by schools at all. These measures should be **financed by an earmarked contribution provided by the state** to kindergartens and primary and secondary schools, including special needs schools. The amount of the contribution should be based on the **standardised cost of individual measures, and it should be fully claimable by schools**. Funding should be similar for HEIs, and distributed from a newly established **Fund for Social Inclusion at HEIs**.

Implementing these support measures will require **the strengthening of personnel capacities at all educational levels**. From pre-primary to secondary school, we propose that **each school should employ a SEN teacher or other professional staff**. In the case of smaller schools, SEN teachers or other professionals can sign a contract with an advisory and prevention centre which would assign them to such schools, or they would work part-time for several schools. At all standard primary schools (covering the 9 compulsory years) and at all secondary schools, we recommend establishing **support teams** as part of the advisory and prevention system. At HEIs, we recommend establishing **advisory and prevention units in higher education**. Professional staff at schools and in advisory and prevention units at HEIs should support learners with SEN, and also provide general support measures **to all learners** (e.g. advisory services, primary prevention, career advice). They should also support **teachers in customising their instruction** for various student groups. Also, we recommend strengthening external support for children, students, parents and schools within **a unified system of advisory and prevention centres**, providing quality and accessible services, such as diagnosing, advising, and offering preventative and intervention measures.

All the measures recommended aim to increase the proportion of learners with SEN in mainstream classes and schools. We also propose targeted **support for the transition between special needs schools and mainstream schools** using so-called **transition plans for learners**. This transition from a special needs school to a mainstream school should be supported by **transition contributions**. These should compensate the loss of per-student funding to SEN schools, and cover the provision of services by professionals from SEN schools to teachers at mainstream schools. We propose that some special needs schools **become advisory and prevention centres**, and others merge with mainstream primary schools. Also, **co-operation between mainstream and special needs schools** should be strengthened. Professionals from special needs schools should provide guidance and other support measures to teachers and professionals at mainstream schools. We also propose that certain specific tools are implemented to **eliminate segregation of Roma children** at schools, and to support their education in an inclusive environment. There should be support and preventative measures available, along with corrective and sanction mechanisms.

Area 4: Improving the training and development of teachers and professional and academic staff

To improve the performance of teachers and professionals and academic staff, we first propose to make **their remuneration more attractive**, in order to attract and retain quality and motivated people at schools. We propose an overall increase in base salaries, so that the ratio of teachers' wages to the wages of the university educated workforce in Slovakia matches the OECD average.

Teachers entering service should be well prepared for their profession. In pre-service training at HEIs, we recommend extending teaching internships for students and improving their quality, along with ensuring specialised training in general and subject-based didactics, so that graduates **do not gain only theoretical knowledge on what to teach, but mainly practical teaching skills on how to teach**. To achieve this, we recommend assigning more time to training in general and subject-based didactics on teacher training programmes. Also, teachers with substantial experience in pre-primary to secondary education should be the trainers. We also recommend **extending teaching internships for students**. These should take place at the latest in the 3rd semester, and prospective teachers should already be practising teaching in a real school during their Bachelor course. It is also necessary to **increase state subsidies for teaching internships**, so that these tasks become attractive for quality teachers acting as trainers.

Prospective teachers must also be trained in **customising education so that they can address the various needs and profiles of students**. Prospective teachers should learn how to recognise learners' talents and needs, adapt their teaching methods, and co-operate with other professionals in providing adequate support for each learner. Therefore, we propose that **special needs education and inclusive education become mandatory subjects** in all pre-service teacher training programmes.

We also suggest that teachers and professional staff at schools should have **access to quality and diverse in-service teacher training programmes**, so that they can develop further in recognising the talents and needs of their learners, and master a wide range of teaching methods. Therefore we recommend **enabling all schools to apply for projects in a simplified application and reporting process (so-called template projects)** within the EU structural funds scheme. To improve the career structure of teachers and other professionals, **quality should be improved in the certification and assessment of professional competences**. Apart from presenting a portfolio (documenting that the teacher gained relevant competences under given professional standards), teachers' competences should also be assessed by a new tool – **lesson observation**. Lesson observations could be performed by accredited teachers and professionals, and the certifying authority should co-ordinate the whole process of lesson observations and receive state budget contributions to cover the costs of this task. We recommend **establishing doctoral schools** to take over the tasks of current PhD supervisors. They should train doctoral students and develop their research skills, along with other skills they could apply outside of research and academia. We propose that doctoral students receive **more systemic support from their supervisors**, to be specified in **a cooperative contract concluded** between the PhD student, supervisor and doctoral school.

For research and artistic employees at HEIs, we recommend that the salary of the **junior academics should match the average wage of the general workforce with a PhD degree**. Also, **the initial base salary upon receiving a PhD degree should be higher (in net terms) than the PhD scholarship awarded**. The first contract concluded upon receiving a PhD degree should be for at least three years. Such a time span is sufficient to assess the match between the employee and the HEI. We also propose **abolishing the academic titles "Professor" and "Docent" and establish specific job positions** reflecting **the current research, artistic and/or teaching performance** of an applicant. **Selection procedures** should be published **in English** on international portals and people from abroad should be included in the process. We also recommend applying **the principle of open research and education**.

Area 5: Effective governance and financing in education

Our schools need quality management. From pre-primary to secondary school, we recommend **adjusting the qualification criteria set for school principals**, so that people best able to manage the operation of the school, improve the learning environment, delegate tasks and act as effective team leaders can apply for this position. School principals should be able to **formulate long-term development goals for their schools** and implement them in practice, together with teachers, professional staff, students, parents and school founders. To achieve this, school principals should be relieved of their operational duties, and receive quality training in a broad range of educational programmes.

Schools at all educational levels need **access to methodological and administrative support** provided by the school founders, self-governments and state administration. We recommend that the competences of school founders are more explicitly stated in the law, and that the personnel and professional capacities of municipalities, towns and regions in school administration are strengthened. In state administration, we propose transferring **competences in education from the Ministry of Interior back to the Ministry of Education**, and from district offices to a specialised school administration. Here, a performance audit should be carried out, and their capacities should focus on providing methodological guidance to schools.

Overall in the education system, evidence-based strategic governance should be applied, making use of data, analyses and experience in the field. We recommend establishing a **Strategic Unit for Co-ordination of Education and Research Policy** at the Ministry of Education. The role and capacities of the Education Policy Institute should also be strengthened, and a **consulting body** bringing together professional and special interest groups in local education should be set up. We also recommend optimising the **activities and structure of organisations directly subordinated to the Ministry of Education**. The Ministry of Education

must make its IT systems more effective, unify data collection and processing, and improve communication with schools and both professional circles and the general public.

We recommend enabling HEIs to set up their **internal structure according to the HEIs particular characteristics, and allowing the management structure at private HEIs to better reflect their needs**. At **public HEIs**, we propose **a simplified management structure** with a single academic body merging the current research council with the academic senate. **We propose strengthening the rector's position**, so that they can conclude all work contracts and participate in the selection of tenured professors. The rector should also **conclude a performance contract with the dean**, and **failure to comply** with this contract would constitute **grounds for dismissal of the dean** upon **the approval of the academic senate**. The **supervisory board should have a stronger position**, and together with the academic senate, they should propose candidates and subsequently select the rector. The supervisory board should comprise **members nominated by the academic senate and by the Strategic Unit for Co-ordination of Education and Research Policy**, or by the Ministry of Education. **Administrative and operational tasks** should be **centralised** and **the quaestor should manage them** for the whole HEI, including its faculties and institutes.

The financing of education and research should be **sufficient, fair and targeted**. We recommend reassessing the financing of pre-primary, primary and secondary schools, so that funds are **available for all educational levels at a sufficient level**, whilst at the same time **improving professionalism in instruction and the efficiency of the school network**. We propose investing heavily in support services for students and the professional development of teachers. Salaries of teachers and professional staff should further increase, so that they match the average wage of the general workforce with tertiary education. **Overall funding of education and research in Slovakia should match the average of EU countries**. It is also necessary that financing is linked to the clearly defined goals of education and research policy. Monitoring and evaluation of measures adopted is also a must.

Introducing **performance contracts between public HEIs and the Ministry of Education should provide more predictability, stability and diversity in the profiling of HEIs**. Financing should also **stimulate co-operation in education, research and artistic activities** across various disciplines. Performance contracts should reflect the long-term strategy for higher education. We recommend **creating a new grant scheme in the grant agency APVV** intended for educational research and research in educational and research policies. The aim is to provide **resources to analyse the impacts of reforms in education and to support a systemic approach to policy making**.

During 2021–2027, Slovakia will again receive **hundreds of millions in EUROS from the EU structural and investment funds**. These resources could provide **the basis for launching many of the proposed reforms**. It is therefore necessary to ensure the most efficient use of these funds from the initial date, i.e. January 2021, and to prepare an **Implementation Strategy of Operational Programmes**. The strategy should be linked to **education reform goals** and should commit to **contract at least half of the funds** allocated for human resources and research and innovations **by the midterm of the financial framework (2024)**. To improve the absorption of funds and project implementation, we recommend **reducing the administrative burden** and the more frequent use of **so-called template projects** with their simplified application and reporting process. These should replace the national projects currently applied, which should be minimised. In order to ensure a sufficient number of qualified project evaluators we also recommend **increasing the transparency of the evaluation process** by inviting not-for-profit organisations to assist in designing the processes, monitoring and informing the public. We also propose creating conditions for inviting foreign project evaluators. In the research area **complementarity between EU structural and investment funds and state budget resources should be provided for**. This concerns financing the infrastructure purchased by EU structural funds, and the financing of research in the Bratislava region that is not eligible for the same funding as the rest of Slovakia. When updating the **Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation in Slovakia**, we propose that **EU structural and investment funds should facilitate excellent research across disciplines**, such as education or social cohesion, which are important for the development of Slovakia. It is also crucial that in the research projects implemented with corporate partners, **researchers should be equal partners to the business sector**, so that they can fully benefit from resources allocated for the research activities in these projects.